

Lower Bounds of Some Small Ramsey Numbers

Decha Samana* and Vites Longani

Abstract—For positive integer s and t , the Ramsey number $R(s, t)$ is the least positive integer n such that for every graph G of order n , either G contains K_s as a subgraph or \overline{G} contains K_t as a subgraph. We construct the circulant graphs and use them to obtain lower bounds of some small Ramsey numbers.

Keywords—Lower bound, Ramsey numbers, Graphs, Distance line.

Figure 1

Figure 1, line distance of G is 1 and line distance of \overline{G} is 2. In figure 2, line distances of G are 1, 2 and 4. This is, line distance set of G is $\{1, 2, 4\}$ and line distance set of \overline{G} is $\{3\}$.

I. INTRODUCTION

FOR positive integer s and t , the Ramsey number $R(s, t)$ is the least positive integer n such that for every graph G of order n , either G contains K_s as a subgraph or \overline{G} contains K_t as a subgraph.

The problem of determining Ramsey numbers is known to be very difficult. The few known exact values and several bounds for different graphs are scattered among many technical paper [1]

s	t									
	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
3	6*	9*	14*	18*	23*	28*	36*	40	46	
4		18*	25*	35	49	56	73	92	98	
5			43	58	80	101	126	144	171	
6				102	113	132	169	179	253	

* Exact Ramsey numbers

Table 1. Known nontrivial values and some lower bounds for Ramsey numbers $R(s, t)$.

For small Ramsey numbers $R(s, t)$, the general method in establishing a lower bound is to construct a graph G which does not contain K_s and the \overline{G} of G does not contain K_t . In this paper, we construct the circulant graphs and use them to obtain lower bounds for some small Ramsey numbers.

definition 1. Let G be a circulant graph with n vertices and i, j be vertices in G . The line distance of line $\{i, j\}$, denoted by d_{ij} , is defined as

$$d_{ij} = \min\{|i - j|, n - |i - j|\}$$

and a line distance set is a set of the line distances.

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Figure 2

In section II, we construct line distance sets in order to find lower bounds of some Ramsey numbers.

II. THE MAIN RESULTS

In this section, we find lower bounds of $R(3, 10)$, $R(3, 11)$, and $R(3, 12)$ by constructing line distance sets of G and \overline{G} .

Since G and \overline{G} have symmetric patterns, in verifying that G does not contain K_s and \overline{G} does not contain K_t we can have one vertex fixed and only need to consider other $s - 1$ vertices for the case of K_s and other $t - 1$ vertices for the case of K_t .

Theorem 1. $R(3, 10) \geq 39$.

Proof: The graph G of order 38 in Figure 3a has line distance set as $\{1, 4, 11, 13, 19\}$, and the graph \overline{G} in Figure 3b has line distance set as $\{2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18\}$.

It can be verified that G contains no K_3 and \overline{G} contains no K_{10} . According to the definition of Ramsey numbers, we have that $R(3, 10) \geq 39$. ■

Next, we have a lower bound of $R(3, 11)$.

Figure 3. lower bound of Ramsey number $R(3, 10) > 38$.

Theorem 2. $R(3, 11) \geq 46$.

Proof: We have 6 line distance sets of G and \bar{G} of order 45, see Figure 4 and Figure 5.

- $\{1, 3, 5, 12, 19\},$
- $\{2, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 20, 21, 22\};$
- $\{2, 6, 7, 10, 21\},$
- $\{1, 3, 4, 5, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 22\};$
- $\{3, 4, 12, 14, 20\},$
- $\{1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 21, 22\};$
- $\{3, 10, 11, 12, 16\},$
- $\{1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 13, 14, 15, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22\};$
- $\{5, 6, 8, 17, 21\},$
- $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 18, 19, 20, 22\};$
- $\{6, 13, 20, 21, 22\},$
- $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19\}.$

It can be verified from each G and \bar{G} that G does not contain K_3 and \bar{G} does not contain K_{11} .

Hence $R(3, 11) \geq 46$. ■

Figure 5. lower bound of Ramsey number $R(3, 11) > 45$.

Figure 4. lower bound of Ramsey number $R(3, 11) > 45$.

Next, we have a lower bound for $R(3, 12)$.

Theorem 3. $R(3, 12) \geq 49$

Proof: We have 12 line distance sets of G and \bar{G} of order 48.

- $\{1, 3, 8, 14, 18, 24\},$
- $\{2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23\};$
- $\{2, 3, 8, 14, 15, 24\},$
- $\{1, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23\};$
- $\{2, 3, 8, 17, 18, 24\},$
- $\{1, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23\};$
- $\{2, 7, 8, 18, 21, 24\},$
- $\{1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 19, 20, 22, 23\};$
- $\{2, 8, 9, 14, 21, 24\},$
- $\{1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 22, 23\};$
- $\{3, 8, 9, 10, 22, 24\},$
- $\{1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 23\};$
- $\{5, 6, 8, 15, 22, 24\},$
- $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 23\};$
- $\{6, 8, 9, 10, 13, 24\},$
- $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 11, 12, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23\};$
- $\{6, 8, 9, 19, 22, 24\},$

$\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 20, 21, 23\};$
 $\{6, 8, 10, 11, 15, 24\},$
 $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 9, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23\};$
 $\{8, 10, 15, 21, 22, 24\},$
 $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 23\};$
 $\{8, 14, 18, 21, 23, 24\},$
 $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 19, 20, 22\}.$

It can be verified from each G and \overline{G} that G does not contain K_3 and \overline{G} does not contain K_{12} .

Hence $R(3, 12) \geq 49$. ■

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank King Mongkut's Institute of Technology Ladkrabang Research Fund, King Mongkut's Institute of Technology Ladkrabang, Thailand.

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